

A LOW-DIMENSIONAL MODEL FOR THE FLEXURAL-TORSIONAL BUCKLING AND VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF PULTRUDED FRP ANGLE SECTION COLUMNS

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ABSTRACT

Due to its efficiency, thin-walled elements with open sections have advantageous applications in engineering. In this paper, a low-dimensional model based on the classical plate theory (CPT) is proposed in order to investigate the flexural-torsional buckling behavior and vibration characteristics of monosymmetric and asymmetric angle section columns made of a pultruded fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP). First, a generalized beam software (GBTUL) is used for investigating the modal participation of different deformation modes on the linear buckling and vibration analysis. The angle section is modelled as two plates and the continuous system is discretized by using the Rayleigh's energy method. Validation of obtained elastic critical loads and vibration frequencies is performed by means of both the GBT software and, for long profiles, a global formulation derived from Vlasov theory. A good agreement for both long and short columns has been observed, confirming the accuracy of the proposed low-dimensional model. The model is used to investigate the influence of the physical and geometrical parameters on the buckling load, fundamental frequency and the respective mode shape.

KEYWORDS

Fiber-reinforced polymer; angle section columns; flexural-torsional buckling; thin-walled structures.

INTRODUCTION

The design of structures with materials having high load-capacity to weight ratio, such as composite materials, has resulted in the use of slender elements, mainly as beams and columns, being in many cases a cost-effective alternative to metal profiles. Among these structures, thin-walled fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) are being extensively used for civil engineering structural applications (Qureshi, 2022).

Although FRP can be produced using different manufacturing methods, pultrusion is the preferred choice due to its cost-benefit, energy efficiency, affordability and minimal waste production. Due to the practicality of manufacture and application, most thin-walled profiles employed in structural engineering have open cross section, which allows a great versatility in terms of shape and composition. Among FRP open section profiles, angle sections stand out for being simple to assemble and very useful in civil construction, being widely used, for instance, as lateral bracing.

The buckling and vibration analysis of thin-walled columns has been the subject of a number of works in the past (Gobarah & Tso, 1971; Attard, 1986; Mohri, Azrar, & Potier-Ferry, 2001). These studies regard the global behaviour of thin-walled members based on the nonuniform torsion theory of Vlasov. However, consistent results are obtained when profiles are modelled as an assemblage of plates using appropriate plate theories. Shan and Qiao (2005) studied the flexural-torsional buckling of pultruded FRP channel sections using this approach. Displacement fields are presented for the flange and web panels in order to develop the equilibrium equations based on the nonlinear plate theory. Closed-form equations to determine the local buckling critical stress of different FRP sections were developed by Cardoso, Harries, and Batista (2014). Approximate functions are chosen to describe the governing buckling modes, in which torsion is assumed for the angles. Coaquira (2020) conducted a detailed parametric analysis of the buckling and post-buckling behavior and nonlinear vibrations of pultruded columns reinforced with fibers, using both a local and a global formulation. Coaquira et al. (2021)

prescribed appropriate shape functions for the in-plane and transverse displacements of flanges and web plates in channels, in order to investigate the nonlinear oscillations and parametric instability of pultruded FRP channel columns. Recent studies on the properties and experimental analysis of pultruded profiles can be found in Cardoso and Togashi (2018) and Cintra, Cardoso and Vieira (2019).

In the present work, a low-dimensional model is proposed for the flexural-torsional buckling and vibration analysis of monosymmetric and asymmetric angle section columns. For this, consistent expressions for the in-plane and transversal displacements are derived for each plate and the coupled equations are obtained by the Rayleigh's energy method. This allows the derivation of critical loads and frequencies of FRP columns which can capture both the local and global behavior of these profiles. The results for natural frequencies and critical loads are compared with the numerical results obtained by means of the GBUTL software. The software performs elastic buckling and vibration analyses of thin-walled members and permits the identification of the meaningful cross section deformation modes through a modal participation analysis based on the generalized beam theory (Bebiano, Camotim, & Gonçalves, 2018).

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The present work considers a thin-walled column of length L with an asymmetric angle section. The longer leg is labeled plate 1, with width b_1 and thickness t_1 , and the shorter leg is labeled plate 2, with width b_2 and thickness t_2 , as illustrated in Figure 1a ($b_1 \geq b_2$). Since many commercially available pultruded shapes have constant thickness, it is hereafter assumed that $t_1 = t_2 = t$. Both plates are modeled using the classical plate theory (CPT), in which the plane sections originally normal to the middle surface remain plane and normal to it after deformation, thus not taking into account shear deformation through the thickness, and the normal stresses to the middle surface are ignored. These hypotheses imply that (Brush and Almroth, 1975):

$$\bar{u} = u - zw_{,x}; \quad \bar{v} = v - zw_{,y}; \quad \bar{w} = w \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where \bar{u} and \bar{v} are the in-plane displacement components in the x and y directions, respectively, and \bar{w} is the normal displacement in the z direction of an arbitrary point (x, y, z) of the plate; u, v and w are the corresponding displacements of the middle surface (see Figure 1b). The subscripts after comma indicate derivatives with respect to the corresponding variable.

Figure 1. Profile geometry and coordinate systems

For small strains and moderate rotations, considering the nonlinear terms of von Kármán plate theory, the strain-displacement relations are given by:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_x = \bar{u}_{,x} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{w}_{,x}^2; \quad \bar{\varepsilon}_y = \bar{v}_{,y} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{w}_{,y}^2; \quad \bar{\gamma}_{xy} = \bar{u}_{,y} + \bar{v}_{,x} + \bar{w}_{,x} \bar{w}_{,y} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Substituting the displacement field (Eq. 1) into Eq. 2, the strain-displacement relations at any point of the plate can be written in terms of the middle surface quantities as

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_x = \varepsilon_x + z\kappa_x; \quad \bar{\varepsilon}_y = \varepsilon_y + z\kappa_y; \quad \bar{\gamma}_{xy} = \gamma_{xy} + 2z\kappa_{xy} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where ε_x , ε_y and γ_{xy} are the normal and shear strain components in the plate middle surface; κ_x , κ_y and κ_{xy} are the changes of curvature.

The resultant forces per unit length in a plate element can be calculated from the integration of the stresses along the plate thickness, as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_x \\ \bar{\sigma}_y \\ \bar{\tau}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} dz; \quad \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_x \\ \bar{\sigma}_y \\ \bar{\tau}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} z dz \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_x$, $\bar{\sigma}_y$ and $\bar{\tau}_{xy}$ denote the normal and shear stress components, N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are the normal and shear in-plane force resultants per unit length and M_x , M_y and M_{xy} are the flexural and torsional moment resultants per unit length. It is assumed that the Cauchy stress tensor components are linearly related to the strains by Hooke's law.

Constitutive equations

Considering the constitutive equations of a typical orthotropic material, the expression relating internal forces and moments to the mid-surface strains of the FRP profile can be written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where A_{ij} and D_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) are the plate stiffness coefficients defined by the following integrals along the plate thickness:

$$A_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij} dz; \quad D_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} Q_{ij} z^2 dz \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The x direction coincides with the main direction of the material, parallel to the fibers along the column length, the y direction with the transversal direction, perpendicular to the fibers along the plate width, and the z direction with the normal direction to the plate surface.

In addition, the quantities Q_{ij} can be written in terms of the elastic constants of the material as:

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}; \quad Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}; \quad Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21}E_2}{(1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}; \quad Q_{66} = G_{12} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where E_1 and E_2 are in-plane Young's moduli in the parallel and perpendicular directions to the fibers, respectively, G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus, and ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the Poisson's ratios.

Variational formulation

The strain energy, U , is given by the volume integral:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V (\bar{\sigma}_x \bar{\epsilon}_x + \bar{\sigma}_y \bar{\epsilon}_y + \bar{\tau}_{xy} \bar{\gamma}_{xy}) dV \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

The potential energy of in-plane loads, V , due to axial compression, is written as:

$$V = -N_x \int_0^L \int_0^b \left(u_{,x} + \frac{1}{2} w_{,x}^2 \right) dx dy \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where N_x is the applied axial load per unit length at $x = 0$ and $x = L$.

The kinetic energy T of the plate is given by:

$$T = \frac{\rho t}{2} \iint_A (\dot{u}^2 + \dot{v}^2 + \dot{w}^2) dx dy \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where the superscript point ($\dot{\cdot}$) denotes the derivative with respect to time and ρ is the material density.

The Lagrangian of the system \mathcal{L} , composed of the two plates of the angle profile, is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^2 T_i - \Pi; \quad \Pi = \sum_{i=1}^2 U_i + V_i \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

where Π is the total potential energy of the system. Finally, the buckling and vibration equations are derived from the principle of total potential energy ($\delta \Pi = 0$) and Hamilton's principle ($\delta \mathcal{L} = 0$), respectively, by means of the Rayleigh's energy method. First, appropriate shape functions for the angle profile are proposed, in order to describe their dominant buckling and vibration modes.

MODAL PARTICIPATION

Generalized beam software

The buckling and vibration modes of the L-shaped profile are obtained with the GBTUL software, which allows to identify the dominant modes as a function of material and geometric parameters. The software performs elastic buckling and vibration analyses of thin-walled members, based on the generalized beam theory (GBT). It considers as interpolating functions a combination of structurally meaningful local and global cross section deformation modes and computes the participation of each mode in the buckling or vibration modes (Bebiano, Camotim, & Gonçalves, 2018).

The profile walls are assumed to be simply supported (SS) at the loaded ends. Compatibility at the junction between the plates (legs) is ensured on the deformation modes, respecting the local coordinate systems. The other two edges of the two plates are, in turn, assumed to be free.

In this work, based on the geometric parameters of the angle section, as shown in Figure 1, the profiles are labelled as L $b_1 \times b_2 \times t$, with dimensions in millimeters. Furthermore, the aspect ratio for the angle section legs is defined as $\beta = b_2/b_1$, where $\beta = 1.0$ means the profile has equal legs and $\beta = 0$ means the profile is reduced to a single plate. In order to assess the influence of different aspect ratios on the modal participation, two angle profiles are considered, one having equal legs (L 150x150x5; $\beta = 1.0$) and other having unequal legs (L 150x75x5; $\beta = 0.5$), both with the same thickness ($t = 5$ mm), as illustrated in Figure 2. The material constants were extracted from experimental work in Cintra, Cardoso and Vieira (2019), and are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2.

Table 1: Material properties of the pultruded material

Property	Unit	Value
E_1	GPa	21.3
E_2	GPa	6.08
G_{12}	GPa	2.31
ν_{12}	-	0.23
ν_{21}	-	0.066
ρ	kg/m ³	1850

Figure 3 shows the modal participation in the buckling and vibration fundamental mode of the monosymmetric and asymmetric sections as a function of the column length, L . For the monosymmetric angle section ($\beta = 1.0$), the torsion mode is predominant while the bending mode around the major axis has a low participation, reaching a maximum of 2.0% when $L = 4$ m. On the other hand, for the asymmetric angle section ($\beta = 0.5$), although torsion is predominant for all lengths, both torsion and minor axis bending modes are equally important, with the modal participation of the torsional mode decreasing and the modal participation of the bending mode increasing as the profile length increases, which characterizes a flexural-torsional mode. Furthermore, a small participation of the local-plate mode can be observed in the asymmetric case for short lengths ($L < 1$ m). As observed, the predominant modes in the buckling and vibration of angle section columns are due to torsion and minor axis bending. In order to use the Rayleigh's energy method, appropriate shape functions for the displacement field of angles subjected to torsion and bending need to be derived.

Figure 3: Modal participation in the buckling and vibration fundamental mode for the angles

Displacement field for angles

Based on the previous analyses, a set of admissible functions for the displacement field of angles due to minor axis bending can be written as (Pires Filho, 2023):

$$\zeta_b^{(1)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} u_b^{(1)}(x, y_1) = C_1 \cos(\pi x/L) \left\{ y_1 \cos \alpha - \left[\frac{x_{cg}}{\cos \alpha} + (y_{cg} - x_{cg} \tan \alpha) \sin \alpha \right] \right\} \\ v_b^{(1)}(x) = C_2 \sin(\pi x/L) \cos \alpha \\ w_b^{(1)}(x) = C_2 \sin(\pi x/L) \sin \alpha \end{array} \right. \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$\zeta_b^{(2)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} u_b^{(2)}(x, y_2) = C_1 \cos(\pi x/L) \left\{ y_2 \sin \alpha - \left[\frac{x_{cg}}{\cos \alpha} + (y_{cg} - x_{cg} \tan \alpha) \sin \alpha \right] \right\} \\ v_b^{(2)}(x) = C_2 \sin(\pi x/L) \sin \alpha \\ w_b^{(2)}(x) = C_2 \sin(\pi x/L) \cos \alpha \end{array} \right.$$

where $\zeta_b^{(1)}$ and $\zeta_b^{(2)}$ represent the displacement field for plates 1 and 2, respectively. Here C_1 and C_2 are the modal amplitudes, x_{cg} and y_{cg} are the section geometric center coordinates and α is the major and minor principal axes orientation.

Considering that there is no warping due to the boundary and loading conditions and that both plates rotate with equal angular amplitudes, the displacement field due to torsion is adopted as follows:

$$\zeta_t^{(1)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} w_t^{(1)}(x, y_1) = C_3 \sin(\pi x/L) y_1 \\ \zeta_t^{(2)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} w_t^{(2)}(x, y_2) = C_3 \sin(\pi x/L) y_2 \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

where C_3 is the torsional amplitude. The use of the compatibility conditions along common boundary results in a low-dimensional model in terms of the minor axis bending mode $\zeta_b(x, y)$ and the torsional mode $\zeta_t(x, y)$. Introducing the displacement field into Eq. 11 and employing the Rayleigh's energy method, a system of three coupled nonlinear ordinary equations is obtained.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the linear results for buckling and vibration are presented. In order to obtain the critical loads (P_{cr}) and natural frequencies (ω_0), the coupled nonlinear equations of motion are linearized and the following eigenvalue problems are solved:

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{K}_E - P_{cr} \mathbf{K}_G] \mathbf{U} &= 0 \\ [\mathbf{K}_E - \omega_0^2 \mathbf{M}] \mathbf{U} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

where \mathbf{K}_E and \mathbf{K}_G are the stiffness and geometric matrices, respectively, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix and \mathbf{U} is the displacement vector.

The linear results are obtained considering only the torsional mode (ζ_t) and considering the coupled flexural-torsional mode ($\zeta_b + \zeta_t$). Thus, one can observe in which situations only the torsional mode is sufficient to describe the critical load and fundamental frequency with good approximation and in which cases the coupled mode is necessary. The critical loads obtained in each case are shown in Figure 4 as a function of the column length for the angles L 150x150x5 ($\beta = 1.0$, Fig. 4(a)) and L 150x75x5 ($\beta = 0.5$, Fig. 4(b)), considering the physical parameters in Table 1. They are compared with those obtained using the GBTUL software and the global formulation proposed by Mohri et al. (2001) (see Coaquira (2020)). For the monosymmetric section ($\beta = 1.0$), all the methodologies provide similar results, demonstrating the predominance of torsion and that the torsional mode (ζ_t) is sufficient to describe the linear response, in agreement with Figure 3(a). On the other hand, for the asymmetric section ($\beta = 0.5$), the torsional mode alone does not adequately describe the linear behavior, due to the predominance of the flexural-torsional mode, in accordance with Figure 3(b), while the proposed coupled model ($\zeta_b + \zeta_t$) shows a good agreement with the GBTUL and global formulation for all lengths.

Figure 4: Critical loads as a function of the column length

The natural frequencies as a function of the column length are shown in Figure 5 considering the same profiles. For the monosymmetric section ($\beta = 1.0$), both the coupled and torsional modes show a good agreement with the results from the GBTUL and global formulation for any value of L . As for the

asymmetric section ($\beta = 0.5$), the model using only the torsional mode lead to higher frequency values, while the coupled model agree quite well with the GBTUL results. These results demonstrate that the proposed coupled model can be used adequately for the nonlinear dynamic analysis of this type of structure, a work in progress.

Figure 5: Fundamental frequency as a function of the column length

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In the present work, the buckling and linear vibration of composite FRP angle section columns were investigated. The angle section is discretized into two plates and the classical plate theory (CPT) is employed in order to formulate the corresponding eigenvalue problems. The modal participation in the fundamental mode is investigated using the GBTUL software for monosymmetric and asymmetric angle section columns. A low dimensional model for the displacement field of angles is proposed considering the flexural-torsional coupling. Validation of obtained elastic critical loads and vibration frequencies is performed by means of both the GBT software and a global formulation derived from Vlasov theory.

The following conclusions are drawn from this study:

1. Monosymmetric angle section profiles tend to present a predominance of torsion. Exception is observed for profiles with high slenderness ratio, which are more susceptible to bending phenomena.
2. In the buckling and vibration analyses of monosymmetric sections, the torsional mode (ζ_t) presents a good agreement with the other outcomes, adequately describing the linear behaviour, since torsion is predominant in these profiles. On the other hand for the asymmetric sections, as bending becomes significant, the torsional mode no longer suits the linear modelling, while the proposed coupled model ($\zeta_b + \zeta_t$) shows excellent agreement with the GBTUL results.
3. Overall, the proposed low dimensional coupled flexural-torsional model can be used for both monosymmetric and asymmetric angle section columns leading to consistent outcomes.
4. This is a work in progress, the consistent approach is being used to explore the post-buckling behavior and nonlinear oscillations of these structures.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.